

Teachers' Competency-Based Training as Predictor of Students' Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education

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Abstract. Teachers' competency-based training was expected to improve the student's academic expectations in technological livelihood education. In this study, the researcher selected 165 grade 7-10 students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' competency-based training and students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between teachers' competency-based training and students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Regression analysis proved that teachers' competency-based training in ethics, integrity, and self-development significantly influenced the students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The study, therefore, was conducted to further utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. teaching home economics
2. teachers' competency-based training
3. students' academic expectations

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1. Introduction

Teachers' competency-based training and professional development is a continuous, never-ending process that promotes the skills required by teachers in the classroom to deliver the most effective and highest standard of teaching possible to their students. Given its enormous impact on student progress, the professional performance of the teacher is a topic worth discussing. Yet, this position is inseparably linked to the educational environment, student characteristics, and institutional issues. Hence, teachers' competency progress has several factor components, including instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development, and resource management, that affect students' academic expectations. As a result, the educational setting has an impact on students' achievement, either favorably or unfavorably. When it comes to the effectiveness of instructors and their students, the schools play a critical role. Teachers are the fundamental component that, via their skills, potential, and professional competency, significantly

affects the teaching and learning environment. To affect the desired changes in their students, only competent teachers are accountable. Therefore, students' motivation to learn is also influenced by teacher instructional characteristics including classroom management and cognitive engagement wherein teachers can get that through various training programs that provide skills and contemporary pedagogical tactics for them to better connect with, manage, and instruct their students in a way that assures that all students are learning and gaining from the experience. In this view, Grauwe and Varghese (2015) focus on the key factors for improving quality education rather than on teacher competence. Achieving a high quality of education in the era of education for all is not simple. As highlighted by Kanu (2012), apart from the quantitative dimension, the qualitative dimension is also staggering in its proportion. Hence, massive numbers of teachers at the secondary level lack qualifications and also training. Thus, this would lead to deficiency and poor academic performance of students, and this could be traced to a lack of teachers' competence and learning resources in the classroom (Nwosu, 2015). The importance of the relationship between teacher competence and student achievement should be considered in improving the quality of education. Prior research has shown that several factors influence students' achievement. For instance, Sali-Ot (2011) argues that the criticism and motivation of the students by the teacher are of great importance to their academic performance. Thus, motivation in students is considered an important factor in student learning. Another factor affecting student achievement is the absence of family and peer support. The family and peer behavior, attitude, and approach toward the child affect the development of the child's personality (Kaya et al., 2012). Similarly, according to the study conducted by Satir (2013), academic performance is predicted to be higher for those reared in families that care, solve problems fairly, establish a conducive environment for learning, set plans, and have a positive outlook on life. Students who want to succeed academically will anticipate their families' active support and interest in both the school and themselves (Aslanargun et al., 2016). Moreover, in a study conducted by Gaji (2014), teachers with a deeper understanding of the subject area generated better students than those with a shallow experience. Thus, it means that a capable teacher must effectively transmit the subject's fundamental knowledge and skills in addition to possessing them. They should be able to organize the subject matter, consider societal changes, and make decisions (Omoogun, 2009). Effective teaching necessitates that the teacher has a solid understanding of all that the students need to know (Offorma Ogah, 2013). However, teachers are perceived to have low enthusiasm toward teaching because of poor subject content knowledge and pedagogical skills due to lack of training. These factors tend to have impacted negatively on students' performance (Jadamas 2014). Malik et. al. (2018) opined that providing effective teachers is to attain high student achievement. Students' performance is indicative of teachers' performance. Relative to this, according to Makombe et. al. (2010), students' academic result is considered a main source for teachers' evaluation. Although earlier studies have shown a connection between teaching competency-based training and students' academic expectations, there has only been a small amount of study on the junior high school level. Also, the researcher has not yet come across regression analysis on these variables. Therefore, the need exists for more outstanding studies in this area. Thus, it was in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Cluster 6 Schools, Davao City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design to understand the influence of teacher competency-

based training and students' academic expectations, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the factors affecting student academic expectations in technological livelihood education in the Davao City context.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research, which was designed to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic, and objective stances. It focuses on numeric and unchanging data and detailed, convergent reasoning, generating a variety of ideas about a research problem (Babbie et al., 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013), correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and helped describe the relationship of the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also looked into the relationship between two variables— Teachers' competency-based training and students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education. The study aimed to investigate which domains of teachers' competency-based training significantly influence students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the Grade 7-10 students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. In this study, the 165 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified

random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only the bonafide enrolled Grade 7-10 students with good moral character and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the students.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed the researcher-made questionnaires drafted to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part was about the teachers' competency-based training, distributed among the four indicators: instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development, and resource management. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers' competency-based training, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Students' Academic Expectations in Technological and Livelihood Education

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is never manifested.

The second part of the instrument was about students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education. The instrument was composed of items divided into four parts: learning interest, peer support, student conduct, and schema. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.85. In

answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the schools division superintendent and then to the school princi-

pals of the elementary public schools in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. The study was conducted in the Second Quarter of S.Y. 2023-2024. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. Moreover, the study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to

Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Students’ Academic Expectations in Technological and Livelihood Education

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is often-times manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education is never manifested.

quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent’s scores were tallied

to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers’ competency-based training and students’ academic expectations in technological livelihood education in Cluster 6, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers’ competency-based training) and dependent

(students’ academic expectations in technological livelihood education) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by *r*. This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple linear regression was applied to evaluate which domains of teachers’ competency-based training significantly influence the students’ academic expectations in technological livelihood education in Cluster 6, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as explained in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers’ competency-based training and students’ academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City; the significant relationship be-

tween teachers' competency-based training and students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City; and the domains of teachers' competency-based training significantly influence the students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

The Summary of Teachers' Competency-Based Training in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Lastly, Table 1 summarizes teachers' competency-based training in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of teachers' competency-based training is 3.76, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed among the respondents. More so, teachers' competency-based training in terms of instructional management acquired the highest mean score of 3.87, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while teachers' competency-based training in terms of self-development got the lowest mean score of 3.65, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the grade 7-10 students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This implies that teachers undergo targeted training programs designed to enhance

their abilities in areas such as subject matter expertise, pedagogical skills, classroom management, assessment, and technology integration into instruction. The result is in agreement with Best et al.'s (2018) idea that in this training, teachers undergo targeted training programs designed to enhance their abilities in areas such as subject matter expertise, pedagogical skills, classroom management, assessment, and the integration of technology into instruction. The training is for promoting an excellent education, inclusiveness, and equity in schools, it is crucial to adequately prepare teachers for the position. Adding more, the result supports Pisani's et. al (2022) proposition that competency-based training allows for personalized and customized professional development for teachers. Teachers can receive training tailored to their individual needs, enabling them to address specific challenges and excel in areas where improvement is required.

Table 1. Summary of Teachers' Competency-Based Training in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Instructional Management	3.87	Extensive
Ethics and Integrity	3.77	Extensive
Self-development	3.65	Extensive
Resource Management	3.73	Extensive
Overall mean	3.76	Extensive

Summary of Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

As shown in Table 2, is the summary of students' academic expectations in technological

livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education obtained an overall mean score of 3.54 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as oftentimes

manifested by the students. Adding more, results on the table show that students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education in terms of student conduct acquired the highest mean score of 3.80, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, students' academic expectations in technological livelihood education in terms of peer support acquired the lowest mean score of 3.39, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested.

Table 2. Summary of Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Learning Interest	3.55	Extensive
Peer Support	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Student's Conduct	3.80	Extensive
Schema	3.43	Extensive
Overall	3.54	Extensive

The result implies that the specific educational goals, standards, and outcomes that students anticipate achieving in this field of study are oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This result is in agreement with the view of Narad and Abdullah (2016) that extensive expectations drive students to seek advanced skill development in various technical and vocational areas. They aim to master complex skills relevant to their chosen career paths. Adding more, the result supports the idea of Shakeel and Peterson (2020) that students with high-level expectations in TLE are focused on career readiness. They anticipate being well-prepared to enter the workforce immediately after completing their education.

Relationship Between Teachers' Competency-Based Training and Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary

Moreover, the table also shows that teachers' competency-based training in instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development,

Schools in Davao City

The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers' competency-based training and academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that teachers' competency-based training has a significant positive relationship with the academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .964, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the teachers' competency-based training changes, the extent of academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students also significantly changes.

and resource management is significantly correlated with academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students,

Table 3. Relationship Between Teachers’ Competency-Based Training and Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Teachers’ Competency-Based Training	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Instructional Management	0.888*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Ethics and Integrity	0.875*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Self-development	0.673*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Resource Management	0.665*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0
Overall Teachers’ Competency-Based Training	0.964*	0.000	Significant	Reject H0

**Significant @ p<0.05*

as evident by the correlation coefficient values of 0.888, 0.875, 0.673, and 0.665. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers’ competency-based training and academic expectations in the technological and livelihood education of students. This supports Witte and Jansen’s (2015) view that teachers who undergo competency-based training may contribute to the development of more relevant and up-to-date TLE curricula. This can result in a curriculum that aligns better with industry standards and emerging trends, meeting students’ expectations for current and practical education. Also, the result is in agreement with Copur-Gencturk and Papakonstantinou’s (2016) assertion that competency-based training often includes the integration of technology into teaching practices.

Influence of Teachers’ Competency-Based Training on the Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

The significance of the influence of teach-

In addition, table 12 shows that there are domains of teachers’ competency-based train-

ers’ competency-based training on the academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that when teachers’ competency-based training in terms of instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development, and resource management are considered as predictors of academic expectations in the technological and livelihood education of students, the model is significant, as evident in the F-value of 38.389 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that teachers’ competency-based training predicts the academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.602 indicates that teachers’ competency-based training has contributed significantly in the variability of academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students by 60.20 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 39.80 was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

ing that significantly influence the academic expectations in technological and livelihood ed-

Table 4. Influence of Teachers’ Competency-Based Training on the Academic Expectations in Technological Livelihood Education of Students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Teachers’ Competency-Based Training	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Instructional Management	.085	.127	.056	.132	Accept H0
Ethics and Integrity	.165	.306	.035	.000	Reject H0
Self-development	.426	.617	.072	.000	Reject H0
Resource Management	.014	.018	.090	.877	Accept H0
R ²	0.602				
F-value	38.389**				
p-value	0.000				

**Significant @ p<0.05*

uation of students. This table also indicates that ethics, integrity, and self-development are significant when considered as predictors of academic expectations in the technological and livelihood education of students. This means that the extent of academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students increases by 0.164, 0.266, and 0.230 for each unit increase in teachers’ competency-based training. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers’ competency-based training significantly influence the academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

Affirming that academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of students are a function of teachers’ competency-based training, the finding is in line with the view of Nasir and Masrur (2010) that competency-based training emphasizes real-world application of knowledge and skills. When students see how what they are learning directly applies to future careers and livelihoods, their academic expectations are elevated. Lastly, this supports the anchored proposition by Liu and Phelps (2020) that competency-based training equips teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to deliver high-quality instruction in TLE subjects.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of teachers’ competency-based training significantly influence the academic expectations in technological and livelihood education of stu-

dents utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 165 grade 7-10 students in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as the respondents through a strat-

ified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Teachers' competency-based training in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City had an overall mean of 3.76 and an extensive descriptive rating. Also, teachers' competency-based training in instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development, and resource management obtained mean scores of 3.87, 3.77, 3.65, and 3.73, respectively. Students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City have an overall mean of 3.54 and an extensive descriptive rating. Also, students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in terms of learning interest, peer support, student conduct, and schema obtained mean scores of 3.55, 3.39, 3.80, and 3.43, respectively. In addition, the result showed that teachers' competency-based training has a significant positive relationship with the student's academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .964, p < 0.05$). This means that as the teachers' competency-based training changes, students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education also changes significantly. Moreover, regression analysis indicated that teachers' competency-based training in terms of ethics, integrity, and self-development significantly influenced the students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as evidenced by the F-value of 38.389 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.602 indicated that teachers' competency-based training had contributed significantly to the variability of the student's academic expectations in technological and liveli-

hood education by 60.20

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: The competency-based training of Teachers in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' competency-based training in instructional management, ethics and integrity, self-development, and resource management obtained an extensive descriptive rating. This implies that teachers undergo targeted training programs designed to enhance their abilities in subject matter expertise, pedagogical skills, classroom management, assessment, and technology integration into instruction. Students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were rated as extensive. Students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in terms of learning interest, peer support, student conduct, and schema belong to extensive rating, while students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in terms of peer support acquired a moderately extensive rating. This means that the specific educational goals, standards, and outcomes that students anticipate achieving in this field of study is oftentimes manifested. Teachers' competency-based training has a significant positive relationship with the student's academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This means that as the extent of the teachers' competency-based training changes, students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education also significantly change. This means that teachers who undergo competency-based training may contribute to the development of more relevant and up-to-date TLE curricula. Teachers' competency-based training in terms of ethics, integrity, and self-development significantly influenced the students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Clus-

ter 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This indicates that teachers' competency-based training has contributed significantly to the variability of students' academic expectations in technological and livelihood education in Cluster 6 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—Policymakers were urged to develop and implement policies that not only underscore the importance of technological and livelihood education in the curriculum but also align with the needs of the job market and the broader economy. These policies should be designed to ensure that students are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in the evolving workforce. Additionally, offering financial incentives, such as salary increases or bonuses, to teachers who attain higher levels of certification in technological and livelihood education can further motivate and reward their commitment to professional development. School heads may encourage teachers to pursue advanced degrees or certifications related to technological and livelihood education. Provide time and resources for their professional growth. They

should also foster collaboration between teachers, industry professionals, and local businesses to create real-world learning opportunities for students. Teachers may build relationships with local industries and businesses to bring real-world experiences and guest speakers into the classroom. They may also implement student-centered teaching methods that encourage critical thinking, problem-solving, and hands-on learning. Students should engage in class discussions, projects, and extracurricular activities related to technological and livelihood education. More so, students in technological and livelihood education should encourage students to set and pursue ambitious academic and career goals in technological and livelihood education. Future researchers may focus on research that addresses the specific challenges and needs of technological and livelihood education, including curriculum development, teaching methods, and student outcomes. They may disseminate research findings through academic journals, conferences, and collaboration with educational institutions to contribute to the field's knowledge base.

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